

Doctoral student of Karakalpak literature of NDPI named after Ajiniyaz

The writer Biysenbay Bekmuratov, who has his own way of creativity in the literature of Karakalpak, is one of the masters of artistic words who mixes real life events with satirical elements. B. Bekmuratov is famous for a number of works in literature. His first works were published in newspapers and magazines and were warmly appreciated by the general public. At the same time, the first collection of "Ovul hangomalari", humorous and satirical stories called "Let's go today..." was published as a book. In the collection "Let's go today...", the writer has figuratively and artistically described the real-life issues that make him laugh.

The writer's story "What do you say about him" is very skillfully written. Although the scope of the story is small, the content is broad. Gossiping and giving each other a bad name, which occurs among our women, was taken as the main theme and appropriately expressed by the author. In the context of the work, the situation in society, the conversation between two women on the bus attracts many people's attention. These two women start gossiping non-stop from the moment the bus gets off the bus. The topic they are talking about is the life of a girl named Kurtka. Growing up among ten boys, Kurtka's character had a characteristic behavior of boys. She was a girl who did what her brothers did, even smoked nos and cigarettes. As a result of this, the Kurtka girl will not get married, she will not be happy if she gets married again and again. These two women say that their parents passed away because of Kurtkani. Women talk about Kurtka's shortcomings in front of everyone, for them, the people around them are unimportant. Only for them, the story they are telling seems interesting. The writer brings out the following two issues through the idea of the story. First of all, through women's inappropriate speech in society, the words related to the fate of a girl are spoken, the attitude of those around her is mentioned, and secondly, Kurtka shows the factor that caused the marriage of the girl to break. The gossiping woman in the story is depicted artistically, enriched with satirical elements.

Another of the satirical works of the master of words is "Twice I Dropped". At the first reading of the story, it seems that the humorous element is strong. Basically, the writer chooses the issue of trade and embodies satirical qualities in the work. In the content of the work, close friends go to the house of a friend named Janis, and stay there, and the host is not satisfied when Janis puts everything in front of her. The shopkeeper goes to his relative's house to make up for the party. When he goes there, he will not find his owner, only his old mother will be at home. An old woman who doesn't like Janice brings her alcohol. He says that he dripped a drop of dichlofos into it. In this episode, the character of the old woman is depicted with simplicity. For example: - Take a walk, Jenisjon, don't tell anyone. I only love you. There is a picture of a black fly that drips once into each bottle when the bride prepares vodka, but now that you are related, I drip twice. I covered his mouth well. He said, "Never forget my good deeds." At that time, I had an idea: "Sister, bring what you dropped into this bottle and I will have a look." . Janice and I froze where we were.[1.12]. The author personifies the image of simplicity through the image of an old woman, however, he mentions the shortcomings of trade and the harmful effects of alcohol. B. Bekmuratov's conversation "Tartibga vyroddi" is also full of life events. The work describes the life of a newly married bride who has just stepped out of the closet. In the context of the work, a bride comes to the house of Ajar and Azat. Old women on the street start testing the new bride. One of them said that Ajar did not go out, he wore his headscarf neatly, the other said that Azat's behavior had changed, he had learned to be clean, and the children in his house were tidy. , they praise the bride, saying that the children go to school on time, and even the

sheep and goats join the herd on time. At that moment, news of a wedding comes to Azat's brother's house. The old women of the street come to Azat's house in the evening, take an invitation and drink tea from the hand of the bride. All the old ladies who entered the guest room said that the newly arrived bride should bring tea and let's see. At that moment, the bride enters with a robe and a robe. When Andy wants to get water from an old woman sitting on a net, they become polite to each other. One of them waved his hand as his prey, the other as his mother and sister-in-law. At that moment, the bride, who was looking around in confusion, put down the clothes in her hand and said the truth without being shy or holding back any thoughts.

For example: -then you should sit in order according to your age, height, respect. Then I will pour water on your hands. "Now let my mother-in-law prepare tea, and my father-in-law to light the stove outside," he said, and went out. The old women looked at each other in amazement, asked each other how they were doing, and had to exchange their seats and sit in order. [1.14].

Through the image of the bride, the writer sharply criticizes the carelessness characteristic of some brides. The content of the work covers the characteristics of girls and women, such as respect for parents. In short, B. Bekmuratov's works acquire individuality due to the skillful use of comic images and the fact that the content of the work is taken from life events.

Books:

1. Bekmuratov B. "Let it go today..." - Nukus, "Karakalpakstan", 2012.
2. Pakhratdinov Yu. "Satire of Karakalpak". - Nukus, "Karakalpakstan", 1992